

A Qualitative Study on Qur'anic Traditional System of Learning (Tsangaya) in Bauchi Emirate, Bauchi State Nigeria

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Abstract

The *Tsangaya* system of education is an Islamic-based educational system that has existed for several centuries in Northern Nigerian Muslim Communities since the coming of the British Colonial Masters. This paper is qualitative research that aims to examine the origin, development, and challenges facing the *Tsangaya* school system in Bauchi Emirate, Bauchi State Nigeria using historical and phenomenological methods. The paper highlights the origin and operations of *Tsangaya* schools in general and Bauchi emirate in particular and some of the challenges being faced. The paper's findings among others revealed that the *Tsangaya* Schools in Bauchi Emirate are facing some degree of neglect from the government, the Muslim Ummah and other religious organizations and bodies. The paper also proffers recommendations for what is to be done to improve and salvage the system in the Bauchi Emirate.

Keywords: Qualitative study, Tsangaya, Bauchi Emirate

Introduction

Tsangaya refers to the informal school or place where teaching and learning of the glorious Qur'an and other Islamic sciences take place. According to Idris (2021), the word *Tsangaya* is derived from *Sangaya* in Kanuri, which means educational institution. Consequently, the word was altered to *tsangaya* in the Hausa language. On the other hand, the term *Tsangaya* School is known in some places as *Makarantar Allo* (wooden slate School) perhaps due to the wooden slate that is being used in such schools. Apart from the general name, *Tsangaya* has other names such as *Makarantar Muhammadiyya*, *Makarantar al-Qur'ani*, *Makarantar Toka*, etc. (Dahiru et al, 2022). Meanwhile, the word *Almajiri* is derived from the Arabic word *Almuhajirun* which means migrants. It refers to the students who enrol on the traditional method of acquiring and memorizing the glorious Qur'an in Hausa land, it is also referred to a particular place where children at their tender ages are sent out by their parents to other villages, towns and cities for acquiring the knowledge of the glorious Qur'an under the care of a knowledgeable Islamic scholar *Alaramma* or *Mallam* (Bukar and Mangari, 2020)

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It is believed that the Tsangaya System has a long history of existence. Its origin according to Yahaya (2018) can be traced to the old Timbuktu scholastic culture located at a famous centre of Islamic knowledge and scholarship now located in the present Republic of Mali. While Bukar and Mangari (2020) quoting Dahiru on their part traced the origin of *tsangaya* to the reign of Mai Ali Gaji(1503 C.E) who encouraged and supported the establishment of such centres in many areas for the spread of literacy. This system had over a long period graduated many Islamic scholars who later took the responsibility of teaching and spreading the religion of Islam nationwide. (Dahiru et al, 2022)

The pedagogy of the Tsangaya schools

The Tsangaya school system has an unwritten syllabus that comprises a lower and advanced level of studies that exists in five stages altogether. The elementary level was meant for learning recitation and writing while the advanced level is the stage for the Memorization of the Glorious Qur'an as well as the ability to write it off the heart.

According to Bukar and Mangari (2020), there are five stages in the *Almajiri* Qur'anic School:

- i. **Babbaqu Stage:** this is a stage where pupils of around four to five years are introduced to the basic rudiments of the Qur'an they are made to learn all the Arabic alphabets, recognize the vowels and diacritical marks, form letters and finally memorize about ten shorter chapters of the Quran. Pupils in this stage are from the range of 4 and 11 years of age and are referred to as '*Kolo*' in the Hausa Language
- ii. **Farfaru Stage:** this is a stage where learners are introduced to the skill of mastering the reading of the glorious Qur'an with emphasis on the recognition and identification of the distinction between words with similarities that are not easily identifiable. Students in this stage are mostly adolescents usually between the ages of 12 and 16 and are referred to as '*Titibiri*' in Hausa Language
- iii. **Zube Stage:** this is a stage where pupils are made to copy and read the whole of the Qur'an in parts from the last chapter to the top one without the demand for memorization. The aim here was to make the recitation of the Holy Qur'an softer and flow well and to improve the writing skills of the learners. '*Gardi*' which is for students from 17 years,
- iv. **Haddatu Stage:** this is an advanced stage where pupils start the segment of memorization of the Glorious Qur'an by heart, initially the pupil starts memorizing portions by copying it on a slate and presenting it to the teacher and other experts for corrections and observation, after completing this, the pupil could move to the sequential memorization until the completion of the whole Qur'an. Students in this stage who are referred to as *Alaramma* start from the age of 18 years
- v. **Sātu Stage:** This is the final stage where the student writes parts of the Qur'an from memory without referring to the written text of the Qur'an. The student reads out loud to the hearing of the teacher and other experts around the teacher for orthography writing and recitation. When the writing and recitation are found spotless (clean) the student writes the whole Qur'an off the heart on sheets of paper, which serves as the final dissertation project. Students in this stage are called *Gangaran* and they are from the range of 20 years upward.

The above five stages according to Auta (2021) quoting Adetoro go in line with the category of the pupils which in most cases are based on their ages. The first category is called '*Kolo*' which consists of children aged between 4 and 11 years of age. This is followed by '*Titibiri*' comprising adolescents who are usually between the ages of 12 and 16, '*Gardi*' which is for students from 17 years, *Alaramma* from 18 years, and *Gwani* from 20 years upward.

The integration of Tsangaya Schools

During the pre-colonial era, the tsangaya system was well organized and comprehensively funded by the state from the zakat funds paid by individuals and was under the control of the Emirs. However, with the advent of colonial administration, the emirs were stripped of this responsibility as the colonialists were not interested in the system. Paving the way for the government-funded Western education system popularly known as *Makarantan Boko* Consequently, the tsangaya pupils metamorphosed into what is now known as *Almajirai*, thus creating a vacuum with nobody to take the responsibilities of the Schools. (Auta, 2021).

As time went on, the *Tsangaya* Scholars took over the responsibilities and deemed it a moral and religious duty to educate these pupils for the sake of Allah. Although funds were scarce and an overwhelming number of pupils to cater to, the system continued to flourish with the support of the immediate community and begging was still not a norm instead they resorted to odd menial jobs to make ends meet. (Bukar and Mangari, 2020).

With the increasing level of poverty in the country, the care of the *Almajiris* became overwhelmingly heavy for the Scholars who were left with no choice but to send these little boys who mostly come from far and near villages without

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provisions and other essential needs to be moving to houses, streets, motor parks, restaurants, and other public places begging for food.

In its determination to curtail the menace of street begging by children and youth in the name of pursuing Qur'anic Education, the Federal Government introduced the Tsangaya Schools integration program in 2010 to ensure that the Qur'anic school or *Tsangaya* Education is integrated into Western education introduced an Almajiri Education Program where model *Tsangaya*/Almajiri Model schools were established in various parts of the country with most of them concentrated in the Northeast and the Northwest of the country. After the construction of the schools through UBEC, the Federal Government handed them over to their host states through the SUBEBs. The schools according to Amo (2019) were categorized into three models with each model having a varying degree of support and interventions;

Model I schools involve the integration of traditional Qur'anic schools within their original location. There are 101 Model I schools in the country. Statutory facilities provided are a block of two classrooms and furniture, an administrative block including an Office, Store, and Toilets, and a hostel block with pupils' lockers. Others are a recitation hall with store and furniture/mats, VIP Toilets, a borehole with an overhead tank, a guest house, and external walls and fencing.

Model II schools are quite larger than Model I schools and were meant to accommodate more pupils. The 18 Model II schools spread across Nigeria were built to serve a group of Qur'anic schools within their respective states. In addition to them, there are 36 others funded through the (Tertiary) Education Trust Fund. Statutory facilities in such schools are two blocks of 6 classrooms, an administrative block consisting of 5 offices, a library, toilets, a computer room, 2 laboratories, and 2 workshops. Others are staff quarters to accommodate up to 10 members of staff, a hostel block, toilets and laundry, a recitation hall, a hand pump, and a motorized borehole with an overhead tank. Both model I and model II schools were also provided with Beds and Beddings with 50 in each Model I school and 100 in each Model II school. Other infrastructures such as classrooms, pupils' furniture, and teachers' furniture were also provided in each of the schools.

Model III schools are pre-existing Islamiyyah and *Ma'ahad* schools supported in terms of rehabilitation and provision of additional infrastructure. Documents from the UBEC and the Federal Ministry of Education did not explicitly state details of such supports as they did for the two other models. One of the documents merely gave the number of Model III schools supported by the Federal government of Nigeria all over the nation as 138 (Amo, 2019).

***Tsangaya* Schools in Bauchi Emirate**

Bauchi Emirate comprises the Alkaleri, Bauchi, Darazo, Ganjuwa and Toro governments. Being a predominantly Muslim area, the people of the area followed the same pattern of *Tsangaya* Qur'anic schools that are common in most northern Nigeria towns as discussed earlier. According to Ya'u (personal interview on June 23rd March 2022 in Bauchi), it is estimated that there are not less than five hundred *Tsangaya* schools across the seven local governments that are made up of the Emirate. The most popular and oldest among them include:

1. *Tsangaya* of Mallam Garba Gwanki, Bauchi.
2. *Tsangaya* of Alamma Mallam Ya'u Dan Daudawo Bauchi
3. *Tsangaya* of Alamma Mallam Dauda, Jahun Bauchi
4. *Tsangaya* of Alamma Sani Dan Jajere Bakin Kura Bauchi
5. *Tsangaya* of Mallam Ahmadu Kwana Sallah in Doya quarters
6. *Tsangaya* of Alamma Mallam Adamu Gudun, Bauchi
7. *Tsangaya* of Alamma Ahmadu Sabon Fegi Gubi
8. *Tsangaya* of Alamma Mallam Sani Mai Zube, Jahun Bauchi
9. *Tsangaya* of Alamma Mallam Adamu Dan Dabirai, Bauchi
10. *Tsangaya* of Malam Adamu Mai Mangoro, Kafin Madaki
11. *Tsangaya* of Alamma Mallam Yusuf Daudawo, Darazo
12. *Tsangaya* of Mallam Tasi'u Alkaleri
13. *Tsangaya* of Mallam Lawal Limamin Kirfi
14. *Tsangaya* of Mallam Mato Gumau, Toro.

As can be seen, each *Tsangaya* school is named after its founder who is normally the proprietor of the schools, and in line with the tradition earlier discussed, pupils have enrolled in the system on average from the age of 7 and after passing through the stages and upon completion of memorization of the glorious Qur'an students are normally returned to their parents and a graduation ceremony popularly known as *Saukar Karatu* is usually organized by the parents as a mark of appreciation and gratitude to Allah.

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Besides these, there are four Model *Tsangaya* Schools built by the federal government in Bauchi Emirate through its *Tsangaya* Schools integration Program:

1. *Tsangaya* Model School Buzaye Bauchi LGA (Model 1)
2. *Tsangaya* Model School Dungulbi Bauchi L.G.A.... (Boarding ETF)
3. Model Almajiri School, Darazo LGA (Model II)
4. *Tsangaya* of Mallam Māto Gumau, Toro LGA.

Challenges facing *Tsangaya* Schools in Bauchi Emirate

In his submission Idris (2022) has identified poor feeding and, overpopulation among others as some of the challenges bedevilling the *tsangaya* schools in Nigeria, in Bauchi Emirate some of the identified challenges facing the *tsangaya* schools include;

1. **Financial constrain:** In the general absence of earnings, the *Tsangaya* teachers do not have enough funds to take good care of their families; they house many pupils at a time without provisions of food, and shelter. The study discovered that the *Tsangaya* teachers are enduring critical financial difficulties. They lack resources to take good care of their immediate needs and those of their families, such as enough healthy food, medical bills, housing, transportation and many more. According to Mallam Mu'awiya (personal interview on 2nd December 2023), despite their financial constraints, some *tsangaya* teachers had to take the pain of sourcing some money, to settle the medical bills of their pupils, because some parents wouldn't bother to check their children after they sent them to the *Tsangaya* School.
2. **Lack of recognition by the government and the society:** One of the most pervasive problems of the *tsangaya* schools in Bauchi Emirate in our view is the lack of full recognition by the government and the community. The system does not occupy any meaningful position in the educational policy of the state therefore those who pass through it are not considered the same as those who pass through Western education schools. According to Ya'u, (personal interview, June 23rd March, 2022)" we are not being given recognition by the Government and the community in terms of assistance. It is only a few individuals within the metropolis that still send their children to the *Tsangaya* schools." Most of the participants of such schools are from rural areas, so that's why nobody deems it necessary to rescue the schools. Another factor according to Mallam Mu'awuya is that most people consider the formal school more important than the *tsangaya* schools which explains why they are reluctant to assist them. (Personal interview with Alaramma Mallam Mu'awiya on 3rd December 2023).
3. **Lack of proper funding:** Perhaps due to the lack of recognition from the government and the public in general none of the *tsangaya* receives any form of funding from the various governments. The *Tsangaya* schools are not funded by the Government or individuals for the running of their schools or catering for the welfare of their pupils. They are all funded by the individual efforts of the founders with little support from a few individuals/ (personal interview with Alaramma Yusuf Umar on 9th April 2022 in Bauchi.). The little efforts from the federal government through the Universal Basic Education Commission and some NGOs through the construction of hostels are grossly inadequate to cater for the teeming number of *Tsangaya* schools in the emirate. According to him in the Bauchi metropolis alone which has over two hundred *Tsangaya* schools only about ten *Tsangaya* schools got government intervention through the construction of inadequate hostels for their students.
4. **Welfare Problems:** The welfare problems especially those faced by the students of *Tsangaya* schools (*almajirai*) according to (Ya'u) are multifarious (personal interview). First, they are generally homeless with no accommodation. In about twenty sampled *Tsangaya* schools visited by the researchers in the Bauchi metropolis, it is discovered that there is no infrastructure other than the house of the *alaramma*, the *almajirai* sleep in the outer rooms of the *alaramma*'s house, in congested rented stalls, or uncompleted buildings. In some cases, there are some selected *tsangaya* schools such as the *tsangaya* of Mallam Ya'u Dan Daudawo in Kofar Dumi quarters in Bauchi, the *tsangaya* of Mallam Sha'aya'u in Jahun quarter, the *Tsangaya* of Gwani Garba in Kobi Quarters also in Bauchi were some buildings were erected through the intervention of the Universal Basic Education Commission (UBEC) (personal interview with Alaramma Yusuf Umar on 9th April 2022 in Bauchi.). Secondly, most of the *Almajirai* have to beg to get food. Only a few *tsangaya* schools such as the *tsangaya* of Sheikh Abdulkadir Musa Jahun and that of Liman Mallam Inuwa Jahun where we discovered that their students don't engage in begging for food. The disadvantages of begging by *almajirai* are numerous. In addition to wasting away a large chunk of their time that they could have used in their Qur'anic studies, begging also exposes them to all sorts of deviant behaviour and immoral practices. Thirdly, as mentioned earlier, most of the *tsangaya* schools *almajirai* have no form of healthcare facility whatsoever (Haruna & Bari, 2019). When they become sick, their *alaramma* does not have the financial capacity to take them to hospitals or even buy drugs for them. Fourthly, most of the *almajirai* do not enjoy other necessities of life

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such as clothing, shoes, and bedding materials. This is why they are always seen barefooted and in tattered clothes thus, leaving most of them in perpetual dirt with the resultant increased risk of diseases.

5. **Inadequacy and neglect of the Tsangaya integrated schools:** The inadequate number of newly constructed model Tsangaya schools is also another challenge for the Tsangaya schools in the area. According to Alaramma Ya'u (personal interview, June 23rd March 2022 in Bauchi), the introduction of the *Tsangaya* model schools did not solve the challenges facing the Tsangaya schools in the area because according to him considering the number of *Tsangaya* schools in the emirate (which according to him are over 500) four Tsangaya model schools are grossly inadequate. Our investigation shows that out of the four Tsangaya model schools in Bauchi emirate only that of Buzaye in Bauchi local government is properly functional. Poor or lack of maintenance of the existing schools, non-regular payment of salaries and allowances, improper medical facilities, and absence of a feeding program, among others are some of the problems that bedevilled the smooth running of the schools. (Mallam Jamilu Yahaya personal interview on 24th May 2022 in Bauchi)

Conclusion

The *Tsangaya* system of education is an Islamic educational system that had existed for several centuries in Northern Nigerian Muslim Communities before the arrival of the British colonialists. The system which graduated many Islamic scholars continued to flourish with the support of the traditional institutions and the immediate community. The traditional arrangement of the *Tsangaya* Qur'anic schools in the Bauchi Emirate is not different from what is obtainable in other *Tsangaya* schools in other states in Northern Nigeria. It has been clearly explained in the write-up that the *tsangaya* system in Bauchi Emirate is facing a lot of challenges. These challenges vary from the poor physical infrastructure that exists in most of the schools to limited curricula to the lack of recognition of the system down to the very deplorable welfare conditions of the *Almajirai* unless these challenges are promptly addressed; they are likely to have disastrous consequences to the development of the emirate and the state in general.

Recommendations

Given the foregoing explanations on the challenges and conditions of *Tsangaya*/Qur'anic schools in Bauchi Emirate, the following measures are hereby recommended as a solution for effective sustenance and integration of the *Tsangaya*/Qur'anic schools in Bauchi Emirate.

1. While all stakeholders have important roles to play in solving these problems the role of the Government in collaboration with the rich people and other voluntary donor agencies is very critical. Needless to say, there is a need for strong political will on the part of the various arms and levels of government which should translate into good policy formulation, appropriate legislation, proper funding, and strong implementation.
2. There is a need for Islamic scholars and Muslim societies to enlighten the Muslims especially the wealthy on the virtue of philanthropy by assisting the *tsangaya* schools either through the erection of physical structures, provision of food items and other incentives to both the teachers and pupils, this will go a long way in ameliorating some of the challenges bedevilling the *tsangaya* schools in Bauchi Emirate.
3. In the same vein, Muslim groups, societies and Islamic scholars should intensify efforts to enlighten the Muslim Ummah on the institution of *Waqf* and the need for its establishment so that the *tsangaya* schools can be managed and funded properly through its proceeds.
4. The stakeholders should cautiously compose an implementable curriculum for the *Tsangaya* schools and it should contain some aspect of skills acquisition and entrepreneurship. Qualified personnel to train the teachers and their pupils should be hired. The trade skills might include depending on the participants; Carpentry, Tailoring, Shoemaking, Islamic calligraphy, electrical installation, and computers. This will in our view provide job opportunities for the products of these Qur'anic schools.

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